

A Quasi Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Black Cumin Water on Involution of Uterus Among Postnatal Mothers in People's Hospital Bhopal (M.P.)

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ABSTRACT

Involution of uterus is a process in which uterus size is reduced and become pregravid in shape and Size. It begins soon after the placenta expulsion and lasts & for approximately 6 week (42 day). At the timed delivery the uterus size is 20 X 12 X 7.5 cm approximately and it is about 1000 gm in weight. In this study a Quasi- experimental research design (two groups are pre-test and post -test design) and qualitative evaluative approach is used. The sample consisted of 30 post-natal mothers, by using purposive sampling technique. The conceptual frame work is used for the study was Roy adaptation modal of goal attainment. Pre-test was administered to mothers after two days of delivery in both groups and post-test administered after 12 days of the delivery. Experimental group pre-test 15 (100%) of post-natal mothers having poor involution of uterus, 00 (0%) of post-natal mothers having average involution of uterus, 00 (0%) of post-natal mothers having good involution of uterus. Control group pre-test 15 (100%) of 00 (0%) of post-natal mothers having average involution of uterus, 00 (0%) of post-natal mothers having good involution of uterus. Post-test in experimental group 00 (0%) of post-natal mothers having poor involution of uterus, 01 (7%) of post-natal mothers having average involution of uterus, 14 (93%) of post-natal mothers having good involution of uterus and control group in post-test 00 (0%) of post-natal mothers having poor involution of uterus, 12 (87%) of post-natal mothers having average involution of uterus, 03 (13%) of post-natal mothers having good involution of uterus . The t value is found to be with the significance level of p value 0.05.

This study revealed significant progress in involution of uterus among postnatal mothers of experimental group after providing the black cumin water for 10 days after 2nd days of delivery (100 ml water, three times in a day). Black cumin water is found to be safe and beneficial for postnatal mothers.

KEY WORDS: Assess, effectiveness, black cumin water, involution of uterus, post-natal mothers.

INTRODUCTION:

Involution of uterus is a process in which uterus size is reduced and becomes pregravid in shape and size. It begins soon after the placenta expulsion and lasts & for approximately 6 week (42 day).^[1] At the timed delivery (fullterm gestation) the uterus size is 20 X 12 X 7.5 cm approximately and weight about 1000 gm. After involution, uterus is reverted to pregravid

state and weight of uterus approximate 60 gm.^[2]

Puerperium is the 6 weeks following childbirth during which the body tissues, especially the pelvic organs revert back approximately to the pre-pregnant state both anatomical and physiological.^[3]

Circulatory system, harmons and internal reproduction system of mother resumes back to pregravid state.

Kumari L Sajithara, Remya R, Chithra (2022), Conducted a study in District hospital, Neyyattinkara. on effects of black cumin water on involution of uterus among primi postnatal mothers. They used quasi-experimental research approach. By using non probability purposive sampling technique, total 60 sample were selected among post-natal mothers, 30 were in control group and 30 were in experimental group. Data were collected by observational rating

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scale within 24 hours of delivery, intervention was given in 90ml of black cumin water which was administered for 3 times per day for 03 days. and analyzed by using 't' test. Result shows that there was a significant difference in the involution of uterus in experimental group there are no association between involution of uterus among primi postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables.^[11]

Black cumin is very use full seed that can be explored for safe and effective medicine for human health.^[4-5].

OBJECTIVE:

- ❖ To measure fundal height & administer pretest to post-natal mother in experimental and control group.
- ❖ To give the black cumin leukewarm water (boiled with black cumin seeds), three times a day for 3 days to experimental group of post-natal mother.
- ❖ To assess the post-test on experimental and control group among post-natal mother.
- ❖ To find out association between post-assessment of experimental group and control group among post-natal mothers with selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESES:

H₀: There is no significant difference between pre-assessment score (fundal height) and post-assessment score in experimental group among post-natal mothers after administration of black cumin water.

H₁: There is a significant difference between pre-assessment score (fundal height) and post-assessment score in experimental group among post-natal mothers after administration of black cumin water.

INCLUSIVE CRITERIA :

- 1) Primi Post-natal mothers.
- 2) Post-natal mother who are able to understand Hindi or English.
- 3) Post-natal mother who are willing to participate in the study.
- 4) Only primi post-natal mothers after two days of delivery.
- 5) Mother who are breast feeding the baby.
- 6) Post-natal mother who has normal delivery.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

In this study a Quasi experimental research

design and qualitative evaluative approach is used. The sample consisted of 30 post-natal mothers, in which 15 are in experimental group and 15 are in control group by using purposive sampling technique. The conceptual frame work is used for the study of Roy's adaptation model of goal attainment. Tool used for data collection was fundal height measuring tape, pre-test & post-test questionnaire were administered. Data statistically analysis by the t-test, p-value is 0.05 and chi-square test was used. The permission taken from institution ethical committee (IEC).

RESULTS:

- ❖ Age: out of total sample of 15 mothers in experimental group, majority (53%) were in the age group 20-26 years, and 08 mothers (53%) were in the age group of 20-26 years, 06 mothers (40%) were in the 27-33 years of age and 01 (7%) were in the 34-40 years of age.
- ❖ Age: out of total sample of 15 mothers in control group, majority (53%) were in the age group 20-26 years, 05 (33%) were in the 27-33 years of age, and 01 (7%) were in the 34-40 years of age.
- ❖ Weight: out of total sample of 15 mothers in experimental group, majority 03 (20%) were in the weight of post-natal mothers 35-45 kg., 10 (67%) have weight of post-natal mothers 46-56kg. 02 (13%) weight of post-natal mothers >50 kg.
- ❖ Weight: out of total sample of 15 mothers in control group, majority 04 (27%) were weight of post-natal mothers 11 (73%) have weight of post-natal mothers 46-56kg. group 00 (0%) weight of post-natal mothers >50 kg.
- ❖ Height: out of total sample of 15 mothers in experimental group, majority 04 (13%) were height of post-natal mothers <150cm, 13 (87%) 12 (80%) have height of post-natal mothers 151-170 cm, 00 (0%) height of post-natal mothers >171cm.
- ❖ The majority of post-natal mothers in experimental group is mothers 08 (53%) live in rural area, 07 (47%) live in urban area.
- ❖ In control group majority of postnatal mothers 09 (60%) live in rural area, 06 (40%) live in urban area.

Table 1: Analysis of Difference between Pre-Test and Post-Test:

Groups	Test	Mean	SD	t test value	df	Tabulated Value	significant
Experimental	Post test	3.5333	1.2037	7.7192	28	2.048	Significant at p value 0.005
Control group	Post test	6.7333	1.0625				

- ❖ The majority of post-natal mothers in experimental group is 12 (80%) are have episiotomy “YES”, 03 (20%) are have episiotomy “NO”.
- ❖ In control group majority of postnatal mothers 10 (67%) are have episiotomy “YES”, 05 (33%) are have episiotomy “NO”.

Section B

Assess the effectiveness of black cumin water among postnatal mothers for post-test in both groups by using fundal height measuring tape:

The measurement of Post-test done among postnatal mothers in both groups. The mean and standard deviation of post-test in experimental and control groups among postnatal mothers on involution of uterus regarding black cumin water. The treatment is only given to experimental group. Mean of experimental group is 3.5333 and for control group 6.7333. standard deviation of experimental group is 1.2037 and for control group 1.0625.

Describe that post-test mean and SD in both groups. In Experimental group mean was 3.5333 & SD was 1.2037. in control group mean was 6.7333 & SD was 1.0625, with t-test value is 7.7192 and tabulation value is 2.048. Which was found to be more than tabulated value (p= 0.05); thus, the black cumin water is effective in involution of uterus among postnatal mothers.

Section C

Association between post assessment of experimental group and control group among post-natal mother with socio demographic variables:

There is no significant association between both groups. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data to find the association between demographic variable with Post-test Score of both groups in involution of uterus among postnatal mothers. socio-demographic variables show the result that of post-test in both groups. Age of the mothers? Chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Weight of the mother, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Height of the mother,

chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Education status of the mother, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Occupation, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Income of the family, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Area of the living, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Gravida of the mother, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Duration of the labour, chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05. Episiotomy applies on the mother; chi square value is found with no significance level of p value 0.05.

Figure 1: Post-test in both groups score according to Mean & Standard deviation.

CONCLUSION:

The study was done to assess the effectiveness of black cumin water on involution of uterus among postnatal mothers in People's Hospital Bhopal (M.P.). Following conclusion are drawn from the present study findings:

- Involution of uterus among postnatal mothers decreases after given the black cumin water in experimental groups.
- Post-test mean and SD in both groups. Experimental group were 3.5333 & 1.2037 and control group were 6.7333 & 1.0625, with t- test value 7.7192, d.f. 28, tabulated value

2.048. These reading indicate the effectiveness of black cumin water on involution of uterus among postnatal mothers.

- Use of black cumin water on experimental group in decrease involution of uterus among postnatal mothers.

IMPLICATIONS:

In today's nursing work or health care team system the role and participation of nurse have changed. In modern nurse are not only provide care of patient but also, efficiently, actively and skilful work as nurse education, nurse leader, nurse worker, nurse researcher and they are also work as policy marker and participate in various collaborative and independent research work at national and international level.

NURSING EDUCATION:

The nursing curriculum should emphasize on care of the present study emphasizes on providing the black cumin water regarding effectiveness of prevention subinvolution of uterus, infection and PPH.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION:

The nurse administrator should organize seminars on effect of black cumin water on involution of uterus among postnatal mothers.

NURSING RESEARCH:

The evidence-based nursing practice must take to assess the effectiveness of black cumin among postnatal mothers' prevention of PPH, infection and sub involution of uterus. Research work need to be conducted the effectiveness of black cumin regarding involution of uterus among postnatal mothers.

LIMITATIONS:

- ❖ Study sample is limited to 30 post-natal mothers.
- ❖ The study is limited only to primigravida postnatal mothers.
- ❖ Post-natal mother who are aged between 20 to 40 years.
- ❖ Limited time was available for the study.
- ❖ The study is limited to postnatal mother who has normal delivery.

RECOMMENDATION:

- ❖ The same study can be replicated on a larger

sample and also at different setting for generalization of finding

- ❖ Roy's adaptation model on effectiveness of black cumin water regarding involution of uterus can be prepared and only given to the experimental group among postnatal mothers.

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